

INTERFACE OF SOCIAL NETWORK AND ENTREPRENEURIAL ORIENTATION AMONG SCALE BUSINESS OWNERS IN RIVERS STATE

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Keywords:

Interface, Social Network, Entrepreneur, Orientation, Small Scale Business.

Abstract: *The study determined the relationship between social networks and entrepreneurial orientation among small scale business owners in Rivers state university. The researcher adopted correlational design for the study. The population of this study consisted of 92 entrepreneurs operating in rivers state university. There was no sampling because the population is manageable. Two research questions and null hypotheses guided the study. A structured questionnaire with a four points scale was used for data collection. The instrument was face validated by three experts and their suggestions and correction were effected. Reliability coefficient index of 0.81 was obtained through Pearson Product moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC). The analysis was done by Pearson Product Moment Correlation formula. The findings revealed that negatively strong relationship existed between social networks and entrepreneurial orientation (diversity and innovations). Based on the findings, it was recommended that; University management should recognize network of African student Entrepreneurs and provide enabling business environment and facilities for entrepreneurial activities in the campus. Further, university management should key into the laudable programme of organized body as to help in empowering students after graduation.*

Introduction

Entrepreneurs galvanize relationships to obtain information and resources to run profitable business outfits. Entrepreneurship research shows that social networks among other things

affect opportunity recognition (Singh, 2000) as cited in Wuver and Schott (2011). Social networks create a platform to galvanize external information as a source of enhancement for entrepreneurship. That is why Bastian and

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Tucci (2013) believe that external knowledge supports organizational structures that are important for change. Social networks are fundamental necessity for business growth because entrepreneurs interact with other people and by that benefit from access to knowledge, skills and other resources. Careve (1995) in Zafar (2012) averred that when entrepreneurs start their business they have a vague idea about how to organize the establishment process, therefore they need the help of the organization that already exist. These contracts may help to validate business opportunity and provide information about the wide firm environment (Bastian & Tucci, 2013). It can also follow that entrepreneurial intentions and decisions could be tied to social networks.

The network of African student Entrepreneurs (NASE) which has its headquarters in Kaduna state university is the national universities commission (NUC) recognized organization for student entrepreneurship in tertiary institution in Nigeria. The network of African student Entrepreneurs (NASE) is a non-profit organization for students and recent graduates of tertiary institution that seek to create support for graduates and students entrepreneurs across Africa and the diaspora. Kaduna state university was unanimously chosen as African secretariat for the network of African students entrepreneurs (NASE) in faraway south end-at-sea campus of the University of Essex, United Kingdom, in June 2010. This was held under the auspices of the Entrepreneurship

partnership for Africa (EPA) –a British council sponsored project and the national universities commission (NUC). The Kaduna state university was mandated to set up a website and coordinate the activities of the network of African student Entrepreneurs (NASE) across Africa. The network, interact on business activities on a well-structured interactive platform. The young network of African student entrepreneurs (NASE) also provide monitoring and support for young African entrepreneurs on all universities and graduates across the globe, taking one city, one region, one nation at a time. Social networks have become essential for entrepreneurship and have also become a major paradigm for the mobilization of resources and the building of trust is needed in business. They are also major sources of motivation, direction and increased access to new opportunities. A network could be stated as a specific set of linkages among a defined set of actors (Sirec & Bradac, 2009). This set of actors could be set of people who have common interests that come together on a common basis to pursue those interests. They also believe that actors in a social network can be persons, groups, and collectives of organizations on the basis of this characterization therefore; a social network could be defined on the basis of the individual or organization. A personal network is defined as the management of relationships or alliance that the individual has with others in the society (Dubini and Aldrich, 1991; Aldrich and Zimmer, 1986) as cited in Sirec and Bradac (2009). Whereas an arrangement between two or more

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firms that involves durable exchange, and sharing or co-development of new products and technologies. In the views of Haas (2009).

A social network is a social structure made up of nodes (individuals or organizations) which are linked by one or more specific types of relationship or interdependence such as values, ideas, financial exchange, trade friendship, social role as well as affection or action relationship. According to Ogunnaike and Kehinde (2013), social networks are nodes of individuals, groups, organizations, and related systems that tie on one or more types of interdependence: conflict, financial exchanges, trade, and joint membership in organizations and group participation in events, among numerous other aspect of human relationship.

A social network helps in building trust among the members of the network. This in turn makes it possible for actors to cooperate and expect reciprocation, 1998, Dakhi and de Clerg 2004) as cited in Doh and Zolinik (2011). The trust that has been built will enable the actors to respect the assumed commitment amongst themselves in a particular network. Network interaction can initiate entrepreneurial orientation among the actors. Entrepreneurship social networks helps to extend opportunities to one another, share information that could lead to the development of self-worth that engenders further creativity. Entrepreneurship research shows that social networks among other things affect opportunity recognition (Singh, 2000) as cited in Klyver and Schott (2011). Network interactions help in building entrepreneurship

intentions because as they interact and brainstorm, new idea recognition will begin to develop into new entrepreneurship opportunities.

Entrepreneurship orientation refers to the extent to which an individual or team has the propensity for the initiation of new ideas, mobilize resource take risk and take overall responsibility for actions taken simply put by Schillo (2011), it is the extent to which a firm is entrepreneurial.

Entrepreneurial orientation can be decomposed into risk taking, pro-activeness, and innovativeness, competitive aggressiveness and autonomy. Risk taking according to Stewart et al (1998) in Fairoz et al (2010) is the extent to which a firm is willing to make large and risky resource commitments. Schillo (2011) refers to the risks individuals take by working for themselves rather than being employed. Pro-activeness describes the characteristic of entrepreneurial actions to anticipate future opportunities both in terms of products or technologies and in terms of markets and consumer demand (Schillo, 2011). A proactive entrepreneur is an individual who is focused on the future and anticipates things before they happen. Innovativeness is the propensity of the firm to engage in new ideas and create processes that may result in new products, services of technological processes (Wiklund, 1999) in Fairoz (2010). It relates to the types of products and services a company has introduced to the market (Schillo, 2011).

Statement of the problem

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A notable concern is the fact that entrepreneurs are quite often faced with the challenge of obtaining necessary information for the acquisition of credit for the finance of their business, as well as possessing the needed managerial and technical skill and experience required to ensure success in their business. This is also true with reference to budding entrepreneurs in Nigerian universities. This is a result of information asymmetry or outright lack of it among students in Nigerian universities, which gives rise to lack of access to useful sources of funds for business. Social networks in Nigerian universities exist and operate in different locations and this diversity should value been a source of diverse information and resources for entrepreneurs. However, the mode of and nature of their operation given the difference in location and diversity may constitute an encumbrance to information sharing, and this is a drawback to entrepreneurial orientation. Absence of sizeable sources of information and finance, as could be occasioned could preclude the establishment of mutual trust and absence of membership support and independence in Nigerian universities, could mar the acquisition entrepreneurship orientation by shortening the patronage by members and engendering low level of self-efficacy and innovation respectively. Against the back drop of the information asymmetry, paucity of finance ineffective orientation becomes worthwhile to diversity and innovativeness of entrepreneurial activities, especially in backward social formations like

Nigeria. For this purpose entrepreneurial orientation is dependent on the nature and dynamics of networks. Hence, the study is aimed at determining the relationship between social networks and entrepreneurial orientations among small scale owners in Rivers State

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of the study is to determine the relationship between social network and entrepreneurial orientation among small scale business owners in Rivers State university specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the relationship between social network and entrepreneurial diversity among small scale business owners in rivers state university.
2. Determine the relationship between social network and entrepreneurial innovations among small scale business owners in rivers state university.

Research questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What is the relationship between social network and entrepreneurial diversity among scale business owners in Rivers State University?
2. What is the relationship between social network and entrepreneurial innovations among small scale business owners in Rivers State University?

Hypotheses

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The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant relationship between social network and entrepreneurial diversity among small scale business owners In Rivers State University.
2. There is no significant relationship between social network and entrepreneurial innovations among small scale business owners in Rivers state university.

Methodology

The researcher adopted correlational research design for the study. The design helps researchers to determine the relationship between two variables or more. The correlational design is considered suitable since the researcher would not manipulate the data. The population of this study consisted of 92 Business owners in Rivers State University. There was no sampling due to the manageable size of the population. Two research and two null hypothesis guided the study. A structured questionnaire was the instrument for data collection with two part: I and Ii part contains bio-data and part II contains response options and questionnaire items with four point's scale of Strongly Disagreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (DA) and Strongly Disagreed (SDA).

The instrument was face-validated by three experts two from Department of Business Education and on measurement and evaluation. The comments and suggestions were utilized by researchers to structure the final instrument used for the study. Cronbach Alpha statistical tool via statistical package for social science (SPSS) was used to reliability coefficient of 0.81 was obtained which indicated a high level, hence deemed suitable for this study. A total of 92 copies of the questionnaire were administered and completely retrieved the researchers. Pearson product moment correlation was used to analyses the research questions as well as the test of hypotheses one to three at 0.05 level of significance. Correlation values were used to ascertain the strength of relationship in the following orders. 0.0 to 0.4 low correlation, 0.5 to 0.7 = moderate correlation and 0.8 to 0.9 = High correlation.

Results and Analysis

The result of this study were presented below:

Research Question 1.

1. What is the relationship between social network and entrepreneurial diversity among scale business owners in Rivers State University?

Table 1: PPMC Analysis between Social Network and Entrepreneurial Diversity among Small Scale Business Owners in Rivers State.

Variable	N	$\sum X$	$\sum X^2$	$\sum XY$	r	Remarkable
		$\sum Y^2$	$\sum Y^2$			
Social network (x)	92	721				Positive
			3201		0.94	High
Diversity (y)	92	683				

Source: Field Survey Data (2024).

Table 2 presents Pearson product moment correlation analysis between Social Network and Entrepreneurial Diversity among Small Scale Business Owners in Rivers State. The analysis revealed that the r-value was 0.94. This means that the relationship between social network and entrepreneurial diversity among small scale business owners is negatively strong. That is, an increase in one variable result to

decrease in the other. Hence, the analysis implies that an increase in low usage of social network leads to decrease in the effective diversification of business activities in Rivers State.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between social network and entrepreneurial innovations among small scale business owners in Rivers State University?

Table 2: PPMC Analysis between Social Network and Entrepreneurial Innovations among Small Scale Business Owners in Rivers State.

Variable	N	$\sum X$	$\sum X^2$	$\sum XY$	y	Remarks
		$\sum y$	Ey^2			
Social network (x)	92	687	2720			
				3103	0.97	Positive
Innovations	92	693	3160			

Source: Field Survey, (2024)

Table 2 Pearson Product Moment correlation analysis between social networks and innovations among small scale business owners in Rivers State. The analysis revealed that the r-value was -0.97. This means that the relationship between social networks and innovations among small scale business owners is negatively strong. This implies that an increase in the one variable result to decrease in

the low usage of social networks and innovations among small scale business owners, leads to poor operation of business activities in Rivers State university campus.

Hypotheses Testing

1. There is no significant relationship between social network and entrepreneurial diversity among small scale business owners In rivers State University.

Table 3 summary of test of hypothesis showing significance of relationship between Social Network and Entrepreneurial Diversity among Small Scale Business Owners in Rivers State.

Variable	N	$\sum X$ $\sum Y$	$\sum X^2$ $\sum Y^2$	$\sum X\sum Y$	df	A	r-cal	t-cal	t-cri
Social network (x)	31	721	3421						
Diversity (y)	31	683	3103	2462	29	0.0	-0.94	-5.21	1.96

Source: Field Survey (2024)

Table 3 presents the result of t-test summary on the relationship between social network and entrepreneurial diversity among small scale business owners in Rivers State. The observed value of the correlation coefficient between the two variables was a negative strong correlation of -0.94 comparing the t-calculated value of -

5.21 with the t-critical value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance with a degree of freedom of 29 showed that the relationship was significant. Hence the null hypothesis was rejected.

1. There is no significant relationship between social network and entrepreneurial innovations among small scale business owners in rivers state university.

Table 4 summary of test of hypothesis showing significance of relationship between Social Network and Entrepreneurial Innovations among Small Scale Business Owners in Rivers State

Variable	N	$\sum X$ $\sum Y$	$\sum X^2$ $\sum Y^2$	$\sum X\sum Y$	df	A	r-cal	t-cal	t-cri
Social network (x)	31	687	2720	2381	29	0.0	-0.97	-5.30	1.96
innovations	31	693	3160						

Sources: Field Survey (2024)

Table 4 presents the result of t-test summary on the relationship between social network and entrepreneurial innovations among small scale business owners in Rivers State. The observed value of the correlation coefficient between the two variable was a negative strong correlation of -0.97. Comparing the t-calculated value of -5.30 with the t-critical value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance with a degree of freedom of 29

indicates that the relationship was significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Discussion of Findings

Discussion of the study is according to the research questions raised in this study. Poor usage of social network and entrepreneurial diversity among small scale business owners in Rivers State shows a negative relationship. The findings from research questions one reveals that poor application of social networking

negatively affect the efficiency of entrepreneurial activities among small scale business owners in Rivers State. The hypothesis tested indicated that there is a significant negative relationship between social network and entrepreneurial diversity. This findings is in agreement with the findings of Jim, (2019) that shows that poor social networking posed an effect on the entrepreneurial activities in Rivers State campus. The researcher are of the opinion that low usage of social networking has negatively affected diversity among small scale business in Rivers State.

Findings from research question two showed that, low application of social networking negatively affect the efficiency of innovations of among small scale business owners in Rivers State. Similarly, the hypothesis tested indicated that there is a significant negative relationship between social networking and innovations among small scale business owners. The findings is in consonant with the finding of Groan, (2015) who opined that non adaptive to new innovations hinders effective entrepreneurial activities. The researcher is of the opinion that poor application of new technology by entrepreneurs has negatively

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affected business operations in Rivers State university campus.

Conclusion

Social networks have become notable as a major paradigm for entrepreneurial performance in the contemporary business situations. This is because interaction in such networks have helped to provide opportunities for resource mobilization and innovation as a result of the synergy that they confer on operators. Social networks with the view to explaining the relationship between network, diversity and innovation among small scale business owners, realized that social networks encouraged as it serves as a rallying point, for innovation, resource mobilization and information sharing.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations were made;

1. The university management should recognize Network of African Student Entrepreneurs (NASE) and provide business faculties and stores to expand entrepreneurial activities in the campus.
2. The university management should key into the laudable programmers of organized body as to help in empowering students for post student life as entrepreneurs.

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